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Research Article

SCREENING OF WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY OF *PORTULACA OLERACEAE* COLLECTED FROM GULBARGA FLORA

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Abstract:

The present investigation aimed to evaluate the wound healing activity of the aqueous extract of *Portulaca oleraceae* (family: *Portulacaceae*) collected from the flora of Gulbarga, Karnataka. *Portulaca oleraceae* is a well-known medicinal plant traditionally used for treating wounds, burns, and skin infections. The fresh plant material was collected, authenticated, shade-dried, and extracted with distilled water using the maceration technique. The extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening, which confirmed the presence of flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds.

The wound healing potential was assessed using excision wound model in Wistar albino rats. The aqueous extract was formulated into an ointment and applied topically twice daily, while the standard group received Silver Sulphadiazine ointment.

Results showed that the aqueous extract significantly enhanced wound contraction and reduces the epithelialization period compared to the control ($p < 0.05$). The observed activity may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids and phenolic constituents, which promote collagen synthesis and tissue regeneration.

The study concludes that the aqueous extract of *Portulaca oleraceae* possesses significant wound healing activity, validating its traditional use and suggesting potential for the development of safe and effective herbal wound healing formulations.

Keywords: *Portulaca oleraceae*, aqueous extract, wound healing, excision model, incision model, Gulbarga flora

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INTRODUCTION:

Herbal medicines are plant based medicines made from differing combinations of plant parts. E.g. leaves, flowers and roots. Each part can have different medicinal uses and the many types of chemical constituents require different extraction methods. Both fresh and dried plant matter are used depending upon the herb. Herbal medicines which formed the basis of health care throughout the world since the earliest days of mankind are still widely used, and have considerable importance in international trade. Recognition of their clinical, pharmaceutical and economic value is still growing, although this varies broadly between countries.

World Health Organization has set precise guidelines for the evaluation of the safety, efficacy, and quality of herbal medicines. Herbal drug is a chief constituent in traditional medicine and a common constituent in Ayurvedic, homeopathic, naturopathic and other medicine systems. Herbs are usually considered as safe since they belong to natural sources. The use of herbal drugs due to toxicity and side effects of allopathic medicines, has led to rapid increase in the number of herbal drug manufacturers.^[1-4]

Wound: Wound is a physical trauma where the skin is torn, cut or punctured. On exposure to air, microorganisms enter the wound which leads to wound contamination and finally development of infection. Wound healing is a complex multiphase process that involves a chain of well orchestrated biochemical and cellular events.^[5] The phases of normal wound healing include hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation and remodeling. Each phase of wound healing is distinct, although the wound healing process is continuous, with each phase overlapping the next and characterized by migration and proliferation of fibroblasts, epithelial cells, deposition of connective tissue, angiogenesis, re-epithelization, and finally contraction of wound.^[6-8]

Role of Plants in Wound Healing:

The wound healing activities of plants have since been explored in folklore. Many ayurvedic herbal plants have a very important role in the process of wound healing. Extensive research has been carried out in the area of wound healing management through medicinal plants. Many herbal plants have been proved to have significant role in the process of wound healing and they promote the repair mechanisms in the natural way.^[9] Herbal medicines in the wound management involve disinfection,

debridement and providing a moist environment to encourage the establishment of the suitable environment for natural healing process. Medicinal plants heal wound healing process by promoting blood clotting, fighting against infection and accelerating wound healing.^[10]

INTRODUCTION TO SELECTED PLANT***PORTULACA OLERACEAE***^[11-21]**1. Botanical Description:**

- Commonly known as purslane.
- Scientific Name: *Portulaca oleracea* L.
- Family: *Portulacaceae*.
- Common Names: *Purslane, Luni bhaji, Pigweed, Verdolaga.*
- Habitat: Found globally, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. It is a common edible weed.

2. Macroscopic (Morphological) Features:

- Habit: Fleshy, annual herb, low-growing, mat-forming.
- Stem: Smooth, reddish, thick, prostrate or ascending.
- Leaves: Alternate or sub-opposite, fleshy, obovate to spatulate.
- Flowers: Small, yellow, axillary or terminal, five-petaled.
- Fruits: Capsule that opens transversely, containing many black seeds.
- Roots: Taproot with secondary rootlets.

3. Microscopic (Anatomical) Features:

- **Leaf:**
 - Dorsiventral type.
 - Epidermis with cuticle and multicellular glandular trichomes.
 - Mesophyll differentiated into palisade and spongy parenchyma
- **Stem:**
 - Epidermis with thick cuticle.
 - Collenchymatous hypodermis.
 - Vascular bundles are arranged in a ring.
- **Root:**
 - Typical dicot root structure.
 - Central xylem and phloem.
 - Periderm may be seen in older roots.

4. Traditional Uses:

- Used in Ayurveda, Unani, and Chinese medicine.
- Treats fever, wounds, dysentery, diarrhea, ulcers, inflammation, and skin diseases.
- Eaten as a nutritious vegetable.

Figure 01: *Portulaca oleracea* (Selected plant)
METHODOLOGY AND RESULT

PLANT COLLECTION and DRYING (Under shade):

The leaves of *Portulaca oleracea* were collected from the local fields of Gulbarga (Also Purchased for vegetable market, Gulbarga) washed with tap water to remove the dust and soil. The whole plant was dried under shade, powdered and made to pass through sieve No. 40 meshes and stored in closed vessel. The plant specimen was identified and authenticated by Miss Rasika S Kapale, HOD, Department of Botany, Smt V G Degree College for Women's, Gulbarga. Karnataka. India. A voucher specimen no. [HKES/VGC/BOT/382758](#).

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE: ^[22]

The drug was subjected to aqueous extraction.

Preparation of Plant Extracts:

Portulaca oleracea was collected from vegetable market and shade dried, powdered in a mixer and sieved, powder of required particle size was obtained (sieve no 40).

Preparation of Aqueous extract:

500 gm of powder were taken in a beaker (1000ml) and macerated with 1500ml of distilled water and 10ml of Chloroform (preservative) for 7 days shaking daily in a closed vessel. After this extraction, the marc was separated and subjected to concentrate at 150 degree C on a water bath and a semi solid mass was obtained.

Figure 02: Aqueous Extract of Plant

PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF EXTRACTS. ^[23-29]

The preliminary test analysis was carried out on Aqueous extract of *Portulaca oleracea* formulation for identification of various active ingredients.

1. CHEMICAL TESTS FOR CARBOHYDRATES:

Molisch's (General test): To 2-3 ml of extract add few drops of alpha naphthol, it is shaken well then add concentrated H₂SO₄ from sides of the test tube. Violet ring was noticed at junction of two liquids.

Tests for Reducing Sugars:

a. Fehling's reagent test: For one-minute boil 1ml of Fehling's A and B then add some amount of test solution and again boil for 5-10 min in water bath then notice for yellow colour, then precipitate of brick red.

b. Benedict's reagent test: Mix equal volume of test solution and benedict reagent was taken in test tube and heated for 5 min on water bath. Depending on amount of reducing sugar in extract the solution may appear green, yellow or red.

Tests for Monosaccharide:

Barfoed reagent test: Heat equal amount of test solution and Barfoed reagent on water bath for 1-2 min, then cooled it and then notice for any red precipitate.

Test for Hexose Sugars:

Test for Cobalt-chloride: Cool 3 ml of test solution with 2ml cobalt chloride then on NaOH solution added FeCl₃ drops. Presence of Glucose is observed as greenish blue and Fructose is observed for purplish colour and mixture of glucose and fructose is observed as greenish blue on upper layer and lower layer purplish for fructose.

Non-Reducing Sugars test:

a. For presence of non-reducing sugars test like Fehling's and Benedict's were conducted.
b. Test for Starch using tannic acid: Extract solution was observed for precipitation against 20% tannic acid.

2. PROTEIN TESTS:

a) Biuret (General test): To 3 ml of test solution add 4% NaOH and add few drops of 1% CuSO₄ and then notice for violet or pink colour.

b) Millon's reagent test: White precipitate appears when 3ml test solution was mixed with 5ml Millon's reagent. In observation precipitate converts to brick red colour.

c) Xanthoprotein test (For tyrosine or tryptophan containing protein): A white precipitate is observed when 3ml extract solution was added with 1ml concentrated sulphuric acid.

d) Protein containing sulphur test: 5ml of extract solution was mixed with 2 ml 40% NaOH and 10% lead acetate solution of 2 drops is added, Solution turns black or brownish after boiling due to PbS formation.

e) Chemical test for precipitation: Test solution was added to the following reagents and any presence / absence of precipitate was observed:

- (i) Absolute alcohol
- (ii) 5% mercuric chloride solution
- (iii) 5% Copper sulphate pentahydrate solution
- (iv) 5% lead acetate solution
- (v) 5% ammonium sulphate solution

3. CHEMICAL TESTS FOR STEROIDS:

a) Salkowski Reaction: To 2ml extract solution, about 2ml chloroform and 2 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added and Red colour was observed for chloroform layer and acid layer for fluorescence.

b) Liebermann-Burchard Reaction: Chloroform was mixed with 2ml of test solution and then add 1-2 ml acetic anhydride and 2 drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ from one side of test tube and notice for red, blue and green colour one after another.

c) Liebermann reaction test: 3 ml acetic anhydride was mixed with 3ml of extract solution and heated then cooled and then add few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid which gives blue colour.

4. AMINO ACIDS TEST:

a) Ninhydrin solution test (General test): To 3ml of test solution add 3drops of 5% Ninhydrin solution and heat on H₂O bath for 10 min. It gives purple or blue colour.

b) Tyrosine test: 3 drops of Million's reagent indicating presence of Tyrosine was added to 3ml of test solution and heated. Solution turns dark red colour in observation.

c) Test for tryptophan: A few drops of glyoxalic acid were added to test solution (3ml) and then add concentrated H₂SO₄ was added. A ring of reddish violet colour was noticed at junction of two layers.

5. GLYCOSIDES TEST:

1) General test: Part A: Take 200 mg of extract with 5ml dilute (10%) H₂SO₄ in a test tube on a water bath at temperature of 1000 C for 2 min then it was centrifuged or filtered it then pipette off supernatant (or filtrate). The acid extract was neutralized with 5% sodium hydroxide and volume of NaOH was added and then going on add 0.1 ml of Fehling A solution and then Fehling B solution until it become alkaline (test with pH paper) and heated on a water bath for 2min. Red precipitate formed was noted and compared with that was formed in part B.

Part B: To extract of 200mg used 5 ml of water was added in substitute of sulphuric acid. It was boiled and water was added equal volume of NaOH used

in the above test. To this 0.1ml of A and B Fehling's solution were added till it converts to alkaline in nature (tested with pH paper) then heat on a water bath for 2min. The red precipitate was noticed. The presence of absence of glycoside will be noted it after comparing precipitate formed in Part B which was lesser then that of formed in part A. Since Part-B represents free reducing sugar, whereas part-A represents free reducing sugar plus which resulted on acid hydrolysis in the drug.

2) Test for Free Sugar: The extract was hydrolysed with mineral acid after complete removal of free sugar and then moieties V12 (glycone and aglycone) were tested.

a) Raymond's test: Violet colour appeared when extract solution was treated with dinitro benzene in hotted methanolic alkali.

b) Legal's test: Blood red colour appeared when extract was treated with pyridine along with alkaline solution of sodium nitroprusside.

c) Bromine water test: When bromine water was treated with test extract it gives Precipitate which is yellow in colour.

3) Chemical Tests for Specific Glycosides: Cardiac Glycoside tests:

a) Baljet's test: Yellow to orange colour appears when test extract was treated with sodium picrate.

b) Legal's test (For cardenolides): 1 ml of pyridine and 1ml of sodium nitroprusside were added to aqueous and alcoholic solution. Pink colour changes to red colour.

c) Keller Killiani test: Glacial acetic acid was added to 2ml of test extract and one drop of FeCl₃ 5% and H₂SO₄ concentrated. At the junction of the two liquid reddish brown colour appears and upper layers viewed as bluish green.

d) Libermann's test: To 3 ml extract solution add 3ml of acetic anhydride and heat and cool and add some drops of concentrated H₂SO₄, a blue color appears as observation.

Tests for Saponin Glycosides:

a) Foam test: Persistent foam was observed when the test extract was vibrated forcibly with water.

b) Haemolytic test: To 1 drop of blood was added test solution settled on glass slide. Haemolytic zone presence was noticed.

Tests for Coumarin Glycosides:

A blue or green fluorescence was observed when test solution was made alkaline.

6. TESTS FOR FLAVONOIDS:

a) Shinoda test: To 5 ml of 95% ethanol was added to dried powder and then included some drops of

concentrated HCl and magnesium turnings (0.5 g), a pink colour was noticed finally.

b) To little quantity of residue solution lead acetate was included and a precipitate of yellow colour was noticed.

c) Sodium hydroxide when added in increasing amount to the remains it showed yellow colour, which was lightened by inclusion of acid.

d) Ferric chloride test: Some drops of ferric chloride solution was added to test solution. An intense green colour was observed.

7. TESTS FOR ALKALOIDS:

a) Dragendorff's test: Orange brown precipitate was observed when dragendorffs reagent was added to 2-3 ml of test solution.

b) Mayer's test: To test solution of 2-3 ml few drops of Mayer's reagent was included and noticed for precipitate.

c) Hager's test: To test solution of 2-3 ml few drops of Hagers reagent was included, yellow precipitate is noticed.

d) Wagner's test: To filtrate of 2-3 ml few drops of Wagner's reagent was included, reddish brown precipitate was noticed.

8. TESTS FOR TANNINS AND PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS:

The following colour reactions were observed when test solution of 2-3 ml was treated with the following reagents:

a) 5% solution of FeCl₃: Dark blue-black colour appeared.

b) Lead acetate solution: White precipitate.

c) Solution of gelatin: White precipitate.

d) Bromine water: Bromine water decolourises.

e) Acetic acid solution: Red colour solution.

f) Potassium dichromate: Red precipitate.

g) Iodine solution: Transient red colour.

h) Dilute HNO₃: Reddish to yellow colour.

9. TEST FOR VITAMINS:

1) Test for Vitamin A: About 10-15 Equivalent units was dissolved to 1ml of chloroform to which antimony trichloride solution of 5ml was added, a volatile blue colour was created immediately.

2) Tests for B complex:

a) Test for Thiamine HCl (B1): In 10ml of water dissolve 20 mg was dissolved and add 1ml of 2M acetic acid and 1M NaOH of 1.6 ml was added and then heated for 30 min on water bath and it was allowed to cool shaken well for 2 min after adding 5ml of 2M NaOH, 10ml of potassium ferricyanide solution and 10ml of butanol. Light Intense blue fluorescence UV visible spectrophotometer at 365 nm was observed in upper layer using.

b) Test for Riboflavine (B2): In 100ml of water dissolve 2mg was dissolved. The solution had a light greenish yellow colour is observed by transmitting light and deep yellowish green fluorescence by reflecting light, which vanishes on inclusion of mineral acids or alkalis.

Table 01: Result of Preliminary phytochemical screening.

Sl.no	Phytochemical constituents	Methanol extract
01	Alkaloids	+
02	Flavonoid	+++
03	Tannin	++
04	Terpenoid	-
05	Glycoside	+
06	Saponin	++
07	Carbohydrates	+
08	Proteins	-
09	Amino acids	-
10	Steroid	++
11	Gums	-

EXCISION WOUND MODEL ON RATS: [30-37]

The animals were anesthetized prior to and during creation of the wounds. The rats were inflicted with excision wounds as described by Morton and malon. The dorsal fur of the animals was shaved with an electric clipper the anticipated area of the wound to be created was outlined on the back of the animals with methylene blue using a circular stainless steel stencil. A full thickness of the excision wound of 2.5cm (circular area=300mm²) in length and 0.2cm in depth was created along the marking using toothed forceps, a surgical blade and pointed scissors. The entire wound was left open.

The animals were randomly divided into 3 groups and each group containing 6 animals. The

treatments of each ointment were applied topically once a day.

1. Group I : Control group
2. Group II : Test group Treated with *Portulaca oleracea* Ointment. 1% w/w (Formulation I)
3. Group III : Silver sulphadiazine 1% w/w (Reference Standard)

Until complete healing takes place. The wound closure rate was assessed by tracing the wound on alternate days of post wounding using transparency papers and a permanent marker. The wound areas recorded were measured using graph paper. The day of Escher falling off, after wounding, without any residual raw wound was considered as the time until complete epithelialization.

Figure 04: Creation Of Excision Wound

FIGURE 05 WOUND MEASUREMENT

Table 02: EFFECTS OF AQUEOUS EXTRACTS ON RATS USING HERBAL FORMULATION ON EXCISION WOUND MODEL:

Group	% WOUND CONTRACTION ON				EPITHELIZATION TIME (DAYS)
	4 TH DAY	8 TH DAY	12 TH DAY	16 TH DAY	
Control	17.50±0.32	29.345±1.32	43.10±1.20	48.50±0.67	30.12±0.60
Formulation	30.34±1.12	51.45±0.56	80.69±0.15	85.57±0.65	21.91±0.78
Silver Sulphadiazine Standard	38.08±1.62	57.72±1.94	86.40±0.77	97.84±0.29	18.00±0.87

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The wound healing activity was evaluated by excision wound model in rats.

In excision wound model, it was observed that 100% wound healing was found on 16th day of the experiment on application of 10% formulation. The results were statistically compared with control and found whereas complete wound contraction was found on 18th day in *plant* treated groups. The results were compared statistically with control and found satisfactory.

The period of Epithelization was also found to be significantly shorter for the treated groups as compared to control.

However the results were more encouraging for the herbal ointment.

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